

**PHYTOCHEMICAL SCREENING AND EFFECT OF *Aloe vera* GEL ON WOUND
HEALING**

BY

HAUWA'U ABDURRAHMAN

NAS/BIO/17/1004

SUPERVISED BY

MAL. ABDULLAHI SHEHU ADO

**BEING A PROJECT SUBMITTED TO THE DEPARTMENT OF BIOLOGICAL
SCIENCE, COLLEGE OF NATURAL AND APPLIED SCIENCE, ALQALAM
UNIVERSITY KATSINA.**

**IN PARTIAL FULFILLMENT OF THE REQUIREMENTS FOR THE AWARD OF
BACHELOR OF SCIENCE DEGREE (B. Sc) IN BIOLOGY.**

FEBRUARY 2022

DECLARATION

I hereby declared that this research work titled “**Phytochemical Screening on Effect of Aloe Vera Gel on Wound Healing.**” is the product of my own research undertaken under the supervision of **Mal. Abdullahi Shehu Ado** and it is not presented elsewhere for the award of degree. All sources of information have been duly acknowledged.

HAUWA’U ABDURRAHMAN
NAS/BIO/17/1004

Sign and Date

CERTIFICATION

This is to certify that this research work by **HAUWA’U ABDURRAHMAN** with registration number **NAS/BIO/17/1004** was carried out under my supervision.

Mal. Abdullahi Shehu Ado

(Project Supervisor)

Sign and date

Mal. Muhammad A Said

(Head of Department)

Sign and date

APPROVAL PAGE

This is to certify that the project titled “**Phytochemical Screening on Effect of Aloe Vera Gel on Wound Healing**” prepared and submitted by **HAUWA’U ABDURRAHMAN** with registration number **NAS/BIO/17/1004** has been examined and approved in partial fulfilment of the requirement for the award of Bachelor of Science (B.Sc) degree in Biology.

Mal. Abdullahi Shehu Ado

(Project supervisor)

Sign and date

Mal. Muhammad A Said

(Project Coordinator).

Sign and date

Mal. Muhammad A Said

(Head of Department)

Sign and date

Prof. Nasir Tukur Dabo

(External Examiner)

Sign and date

ACKNOWLEDGEMENT

First of all, I give all Thanks and Glory to Allah (S.W.T.) the Giver of knowledge, the Beginning and the End. Without Whom I could not have completed this project. Words cannot express the outmost help and support I received from my amazing project supervisor Mal. Abdullahi Shehu Ado whose tireless guidance leads to the successful conclusion of my project work. I pray that may his every positive wish become a reality.

I also appreciate the love, care and support of my parents for being there always for me and making a better person in me. I appreciate every help, advice, support, loving and caring you have offered to me. I love you all.

DEDICATION

This project work is whole-heartedly and humbly dedicated to Almighty Allah who has been Merciful, Loving and Protective in directing all of my affairs throughout the period of my studies in Al-Qalam University Katsina. I also dedicated this research work to my parents, brothers and sisters for their love, concern, moral and financial support during the period of the studies.

Table of Contents

DECLARATION	<i>i</i>
CERTIFICATION	<i>ii</i>
APPROVAL PAGE	<i>iii</i>
ACKNOWLEDGEMENT	<i>iv</i>
DEDICATION	<i>v</i>
ABSTRACT	<i>viii</i>
CHAPTER ONE	<i>9</i>
1.0 INTRODUCTION	<i>9</i>
1.1 Background of the Study.....	<i>9</i>
1.2 Statement of Research Problem.....	<i>13</i>
1.3 Aim of the Study.....	<i>14</i>
1.4 Objectives of the Study.....	<i>14</i>
1.5 Research Hypotheses.....	<i>14</i>
1.6 Justification of the Study.....	<i>14</i>
1.7 Significance of the Study.....	<i>15</i>
1.9 Scope of the Study.....	<i>15</i>
CHAPTER TWO	<i>16</i>
2.0 LITERATURE REVIEW	<i>16</i>
2.1 Aloe vera.....	<i>16</i>
2.2 Biological Components of <i>Aloe vera</i>	<i>18</i>
2.3 Mechanism of Actions - Uses and Applications of <i>Aloe vera</i>	<i>20</i>
2.3.1 Cosmetic Uses.....	<i>20</i>
2.3.2 Food Uses.....	<i>20</i>
2.4 Medicinal Uses.....	<i>21</i>
2.4.1 Healing Wounds.....	<i>21</i>
2.4.2 Anti-inflammatory Action and Immunity Activity.....	<i>21</i>
2.4.3 Effects on skin exposure to UV and X-radiation.....	<i>21</i>
2.4.5 Effects on ulcers.....	<i>22</i>
2.4.6 Antidiabetic Activities.....	<i>22</i>
2.4.7 Antioxidant Activities.....	<i>22</i>
2.4.8 Laxative Effects and Antibacterial Properties.....	<i>22</i>
2.4.9 Antifungal Activity.....	<i>23</i>
2.4.10 Antiviral, Antitumor and Age-related Activity.....	<i>23</i>
2.5 The Use of <i>Aloe vera</i> in Animal Nutrition.....	<i>23</i>
2.6 Properties of <i>Aloe vera</i>	<i>24</i>
2.6 Health Benefits of <i>Aloe Vera</i>	<i>25</i>
2.7. External Benefits.....	<i>26</i>
2.7.1 Burn and Wound Healing.....	<i>26</i>
2.7.2 Immune System Restoration.....	<i>27</i>

2.7.3 Moisturizer.....	27
2.7.4 Arthritis, Joint and Muscle Pain	28
2.7.5 Anti-Inflammatory and Biological Vehicle	28
2.8 Internal Benefits.....	28
2.8.1 Arthritis, Joint and Muscle Pain	28
2.8.2 Relieve Gastrointestinal Problems	28
2.8.3 Coronary Heart Disease	29
2.8.4 Antioxidant and Blood Circulation.....	29
2.8.5 Digestion	29
2.8.6 Immune system, Burns and Sunburn	30
2.8.7 Laxative and Detoxification	30
2.9 Medicinal Uses of <i>Aloe Vera</i>	30
2.10 <i>Aloe vera</i> for a Healthy Skin	31
2.11 Side Effects of <i>Aloe vera</i>	33
2.12 Effect on HIV.....	33
CHAPTER FOUR.....	39
4.0 RESULTS	39
4.1 Qualitative Phytochemical Screening of <i>Aloe vera</i>	39
4.2 Effects on Wound Contraction Observed at the Proliferative and Maturation Phases of Wound Healing	40
CHAPTER FIVE.....	41
5.0 DISCUSSION, CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS	41
5.1 DISCUSSION	41
5.2 Conclusion	42
5.3 Recommendation.....	42
REFERENCES	43
APPENDIX.....	46

ABSTRACT

The study assess the phytochemical Screening and Effect of Aloe Vera Gel on Wound Healing. The study was an experimental, laboratory-based study, which was carried out at the laboratory of the Biology Department, Al-Qalam University Kasina, Katsina state, Nigeria. Fresh leaves of A. Vera were collected from the Biological garden of Al-Qalam University Katsina, Katsina, in February 2022. The fresh leaves were washed with distilled water and air-dried. After drying, leaves were powdered and stored at 4°C in airtight bottles for further study. 0.3 grams of Aloe vera leaves grounded and added with 50 ml of chloroform, n-hexane, ethyl acetate and double distilled water in separate flasks for phytonutrients extraction for 48 hours. Also, four rabbits (mean weight 1.7kg), were acclimatized for 7 days and divided into experimental and control groups of two each. The paravertebral region of the rabbit was moistened, washed with soap and water, shaved and cleaned with cotton wool moistened with methylated spirit to disinfect the area. The site was locally-blocked with 2% lignocaine double diluted to 5ml and administered 0.2ml subcutaneously. A pin-prick non-response indicated effective anaesthesia. A pair of wounds (2cm x 2cm each) was created on the superficial epidermis of the skin of each rabbit using a scalpel and thumb forceps. Each wound was lavaged with normal saline using a needle and syringe. The wounds on experimental rabbits were topically treated with the Aloe vera gel dispensed with a syringe. The wounds on control rabbits were treated with 0.9% normal saline. This wound treatment was done daily from day 0 until the wound scabs fell off representing the termination of the experiment. Treatment of wounds in rabbits with Aloe vera gel produced significant ($P < 0.05$) effects on wound contraction, especially during the proliferative and maturation phases of wound healing. This could have been due to the presence of phytochemicals in Aloe vera such as flavonoids and saponins which are useful in protecting and repairing damaged tissues of plants and animals. Also, glucomannan, a mannose-rich polysaccharide and gibberellin, a growth hormone present in the gel could have partly played important roles in faster wound healing by interacting with the growth factor receptors which in turn stimulated the activity and proliferation of fibroblasts and promoted collagen synthesis.

CHAPTER ONE

1.0 INTRODUCTION

1.1 Background of the Study

Aloe vera has been used by mankind for thousands of years in folk medicine for therapeutic properties, especially on the skin. This plant is one of the oldest known and its first documented use by humans dates back to an Egyptian papyrus from 3500 BC. (Alexander, 2015).

The Greek philosopher Aristotle wrote about the beneficial medicinal effect of *Aloe vera*. By the early 1800s *Aloe vera* was served as a laxative in the United States. Moreover, modern clinical use began in the 1930s with reports of successful treatment of x-ray and radium burns. *Aloe vera* derives its name from the Arabic word “*Alloeh*” which means “shining bitter substance” because of the bitter liquid found in the leaves and *Vera* which means “true” in Latin (Alexander, 2015).

Aloe vera is a medicinal plant traditionally used since 1500 BC in many countries such as Greece, China, and Mexico. It also has been used for centuries as a traditional medicine for various diseases and skin lesions. *Aloe vera* is an indigenous plant from tropical Madagascar, Saudi Arabia, and Iran. It belongs to the Liliaceae family; it is similar to Cactus and is a herbaceous and perennial plant with thick, fleshy and long leaves. (Alexander, 2015).

The Egyptian queens Nefertiti and Cleopatra used *Aloe vera* as part of their regular beauty regime. So far, 75 known compounds have been identified in *Aloe vera*, including 20 minerals, 20 amino acids, vitamins, and water. In vitro studies and studies conducted on living organisms have shown that *Aloe vera* can inhibit thromboxane (an inhibitor of wound healing), improve

the wound healing process, and reduce inflammation. Magnesium lactate available in the gel can prevent the production of histamine that causes itching and irritation of the skin. It also enhances the immune system and the synthesis of cytokines. (Aron, 2011).

Aloe vera is effective in inhibiting inflammatory reactions by the inhibition of IL-6 and IL-8, the reduction of leukocyte adhesion, an increase of IL-10 levels, and a decrease of TNF alpha levels. Its regenerative properties are due to the compound glucomannan, which is rich with polysaccharides like mannose. Glucomannan affects fibroblast growth factor receptors and stimulates their activity and proliferation, which in turn increases the production of collagen. (Harry, 2013).

Aloe vera gel can not only increase the amount of collagen in wounds but also change the composition of collagen, increase collagen cross-linking and thereby promote wound healing. Scientific studies have shown that the gel can increase flexibility and reduce the fragility of the skin since 99% of the gel is water. Additionally, mucopolysaccharides along with amino acids and zinc present in Aloe vera can lead to skin integrity, moisture retention, erythema reduction, and help to prevent skin ulcers (Harry, 2013).

Many studies have shown the positive effects of Aloe vera to treat wounds such as psoriasis, mouth sores, ulcers, diabetes, herpes, bedsores, and burn wounds. Aloe vera is known for its anti-tumour, anti-inflammatory, skin protection, anti-diabetic, anti-bacterial, anti-viral, antiseptic, and wound healing properties (Raphael, 2012).

The wound is a break and discontinuation in the integrity of the skin and soft tissues as a result of any trauma and any physical, thermal and chemical injury. For restoration of the continuity

of the skin integrity, appropriate management is essential to recover the anatomical and physiological status of the skin (Barreto *et al.*, 2014).

Wound healing is a complicated process including a series of intercalated circumstances mediated through a number of phases of cellular and chemically coordinated processes along with hormonal influences (Chan *et al.*, 2008). Wound healing has four stages including coagulating, inflammatory, proliferative and remodelling phases, which determine the strength and healing of the tissue (Ayyanar and Ignacimuthu, 2009; Sumitra *et al.*, 2005).

The process of wound healing is a complex biological processes and the promotion of tissue recovery is the main objective of medical interventions. Skin lesions are caused due to different reasons such as burns, arterial diseases, surgery, and trauma (Raphael, 2012).

Wound healing is a dynamic process that takes place in three phases. The first phase is inflammation, congestion, and leukocyte infiltration. The second phase involves the removal of dead tissue and the third phase of proliferation includes epithelial regeneration and fibrous tissue formation. (Raphael, 2012).

Several studies on Aloe vera have been conducted and shown to be effective in the prevention and healing of wounds. Natural products including herbals and medicinal plants have been frequently used in the treatment of various diseases worldwide, for centuries. Above 80% of the population throughout the world is still dependent upon these traditional medicines for the cure of their maladies. Among these products, honey and Aloe vera have significance in wound healing (Kumara *et al.*, 2001).

Aloe vera is the name often used for *A Vera Linne* or *A barbadensis Miller*. This plant has more than 400 identified species and belongs to the Aloaceae or Liliaceae family. The *A Vera* leaf contains chemical compounds (i.e., acetylated mannans, polymannans, anthraquinone C-glycosides, anthrones, anthraquinones, and lectins) and has been traditionally used in many cultures for its therapeutic properties. The mucilaginous gel from the leaf pulp of *A Vera* has been incorporated into many cosmetic and alternative medicines for rejuvenation, wound healing, and other dermatologic conditions. (James, 2012).

Despite its wide use as a folk remedy, few scientific studies have been conducted regarding the physiological function of *A Vera* in wound repair. (Aron, 2011). Previous studies suggested *a Vera*, or 1 or more of its constituents, promotes wound healing in various animal models; however, its mechanism of action remains unclear. Chithra *et al* (2015) evaluated the effect of *A Vera* gel on full-thickness wounds in diabetic rats. Their results indicated *A Vera* treatment may enhance the process of wound healing by affecting fibroplasia, collagen synthesis, and wound contraction.

In a recent study by Moriyama *et al*, (2002) the authors showed *A Vera* promoted keratinocyte proliferation and migration *in vitro* and improved the process of wound healing in an *ex vivo* assay. Feily and Namazi (2012) conducted a review to evaluate the efficacy of *A Vera* preparations on the treatment of skin diseases using an *in vivo* murine model and clinical studies. Their murine model found oral *A Vera* preparation was effective for wound healing; however, their clinical studies found topical *A Vera* had no preventive or protective effects on skin injuries due to radiation, sunburn, or suntan but was effective in the treatment of frostbite and burn wounds. In addition, Feily and Namazi (2012), found *A Vera* had antimicrobial and antifungal effects.

1.2 Statement of Research Problem

Wounds and related injuries remain a major cause of death and disability. Wound healing is a complex, highly regulated process that includes cellular, molecular, biochemical, and physiological events that permit living organisms to repair accidental lesions. This process includes overlapping phases: inflammation, proliferation and tissue formation, and tissue remodelling (Alexander, 2015).

The proliferative phase involves reepithelialization and granulation tissue formation, which includes fibroplasia and angiogenesis. Reepithelialization refers to the resurfacing of the epidermis by keratinocytes, the main cell type of the skin epidermis, from the wound edges and/or residuals of skin appendages. Keratinocytes begin migration 12 to 24 hours after injury (Adekulle, 2014).

The migration and proliferation of these cells are key events for epithelialization and closure of the wound gap. During granulation tissue formation, fibroblasts migrate, proliferate, and synthesize large amounts of collagen and other extracellular matrices to fill the dermal defect in a process known as fibroplasia. During angiogenesis, new blood vessels are formed in the wounded area. Angiogenesis depends on the migration and proliferation of endothelial cells from pre-existing blood vessels in the wound edge (Adekulle, 2014).

The objective of wound management is to heal wounds in the shortest amount of time with minimal pain, discomfort, and scarring. Thus, improving treatment for wound healing and tissue repair will improve the quality of life of patients with wounds as well as reduce the overall cost of wound-related health care. Considering the availability of several clinical trials on the effect of Aloe vera on the prevention and healing of wounds, as well as its popularity

among people and widespread use in the cosmetic industry, the present study aimed to assess the effects of Aloe Vera on wound healing.

1.3 Aim of the Study

The study aims to conduct phytochemical screening and assess the effect of *Aloe vera* gel on wound healing.

1.4 Objectives of the Study

The specific objectives of the study are;

1. To extract, screen and identify bioactive substances responsible for wound healing found in *Aloe vera* gel using qualitative phytochemical screening.
2. To determine the effectiveness of *Aloe vera* on wound healing in rabbits

1.5 Research Hypotheses

H₀: Aloe Vera gel has no significant effect on wound healing.

H₁: Aloe Vera gel has a significant effect on wound healing.

1.6 Justification of the Study

Natural products including herbals and medicinal plants have been frequently used in the treatment of various diseases worldwide, for centuries. Above 80% of the population throughout the world is still dependent upon these traditional medicines for the cure of their maladies. Among these products, honey and Aloe vera have significance in wound healing (Kumara *et al.*, 2001). *Aloe vera* contains enzymes such as bradykinase, carboxypeptidase which have analgesic and anti-inflammatory effects.

The research work is important in several ways both to the health personnel and the individual within the society. Firstly, this study will expose to us some of the biological components, properties and health benefits of Aloe Vera, as well as its medicinal uses and application. This research will also be a contribution to the body of literature in the subject area, thereby constituting the empirical literature for future research in the subject area.

1.7 Significance of the Study

The study will enable researchers to have more knowledge, skills and experience on phytochemical screening and the effect of *Aloe vera* on wound healing. The study will also enlighten the public on some of the health benefits of *Aloe vera*, its medicinal uses and application as well as its effects on wound healing.

1.9 Scope of the Study

Conceptually the study hovers around the phytochemical screening of *Aloe vera* gel and its effect on wound healing. Extensive investigation is conducted on its bioactive components, properties, medicinal use and its effect on wound healing.

CHAPTER TWO

2.0 LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1 Aloe vera

This species was first described by Carl Linnaeus in 1753 who suggested the following classification:

Kingdom: Plantae,

Order: Asparagales,

Family: Asphodelaceae,

Genus: Aloe,

Species: *Aloe vera*.

Botanical Name(s): *Aloe barbadensis*, *Aloe indica*, *Aloe Barbados*, *Aloe Vera*

Popular Name(s): Aloe, Aloe Vera, Indian Alces, Kumari, Ghirita, Gawarpaltra, Barbados aloe, Curacao aloe and Lu Hui etc.

It is a stemless or very short-stemmed plant growing to 80-100 cm tall, spreading by offsets and root sprouts. The leaves are lanceolate, thick and fleshy, green to grey-green, with a serrated margin. The flowers are produced on a spike up to 90 cm tall, each flower pendulous, with a yellow tubular corolla 2-3 cm long. The tissue in the centre of the aloe leaf contains a gel that yields aloe gel or *Aloe vera* gel (Martins, 2014).

Aloe Vera contains an array of materials, including the following. Acids - antimicrobial, anti-helminthic (anti-parasitic worms), wound healing for skin tissue and ulcers. Amino Acids - required for repair and growth. *Aloe Vera* contains twenty of the twenty-two essential amino acids. Enzymes - catalysts enabling chemical reactions to take place. Lectin - anti-tumor effects. Lipids - principal structural components of living cells. Minerals - calcium,

magnesium, potassium and sodium are all present in significant quantities. Lactates and Salicylates - analgesic properties. Phenolic - mild antiseptics and antimicrobials. Polysaccharides - long-chain sugars are broken down to smaller ones via enzymes. Urea-Nitrogen - painkilling effect. Vitamins - contains 8 of the 13 recognized vitamins. Contra-indications/Precautions are not recommended during pregnancy (Martins, 2014).

There are a number of synonyms: *Aloe barbadensis* Mill. *Aloe indica* Royle, *Aloe perfoliat* L. var *Vera* and *Aloe vulgaris* Lam. Most of the Aloe plants are not toxic, but a few are extremely poisonous. There are about four main species of approximately 420, that have medicinal properties and among them is *Aloe vera* which is considered to be the most potent and therefore the most popular, also widely grown as an ornamental plant (James, 2012).

The natural range of *Aloe vera* is unclear as the species has been widely cultivated throughout the world, rather originating in Africa. It is grown in most subtropical and tropical locations including South Africa and Latin America, and then it was introduced to China, India and various parts of Southern Europe in the 17th century (Adekulle, 2014).

Aloe Vera is a cactus-like plant, although is related to the onion, garlic and asparagus. It is stemless with triangular, fleshy leaves ranging in colour from grey-green to bright green and in the margin of the leaves has small white teeth. The leaves are composed of three layers: an inner gel, a yellow sap and the outer thick layer of 15-20 cells called rind. Aloe leaves have long been used for medical and cosmetic purposes as well in healthy foods but there is no clear understanding of scientific analysis of the basis for such properties (Aron, 2011).

According to other researchers, 8-10 *Aloe vera* can be separated into two basic products, latex and gel. The latex, representing approximately 20-30% by weight of the whole leaf referred to as “aloe juice” or “aloe sap”, is a bitter yellow exudate from the pericyclic tubules beneath the epidermis of the leaf. Young leaves were found to have higher concentrations of latex components compared to older leaves. On the other hand, the colourless, tasteless gel is the pulp or mucilage from the parenchyma cells of the plant in the inner part of the leaf 8-10. (Aron, 2011).

Early, in 1941 was reported that the leaf pulp of *Aloe vera* contained 98.5% water and its alcoholic-insoluble portion was mucilage containing uronic acid, fructose, hydrolysable sugars and enzymes. Nowadays, it is known that the gel representing approximately 70-80% by weight of the whole leaf, serves as the water and energy storage component of the plant. When it is used the whole leaf of *Aloe vera*, it is difficult to distinguish if their biological effects are attributed to the gel or the latex because during the gel preparation exudates compounds may infiltrate (Aron, 2011).

2.2 Biological Components of *Aloe vera*

Aloe vera latex and gel have physiologically active substances with biological effects, acting alone or indicating a synergistic. The identification of these substances is important for the effective use of the plant. The chemical composition of *Aloe vera* varies and depends on the climate, region, growing conditions, the age of the plant or the processing method (Harry, 2013).

Aloe vera latex is high in anthraquinones, phenolic compounds that have strong laxative effects while they can act also as antibacterial, especially against Gram-positive bacteria analgetics

and antiviral. In addition, the latex is reported to contain, on a dry weight basis, and acid-insoluble resin (16-33%), significant ash content (24.5%) and a small quantity of essential oil that is responsible for the odour of the latex. In spite of these biological activities, anthraquinones may have harmful effects, such as genotoxic, mutagenic and tumour-promoting. A potent source of polysaccharides seems to be *Aloe vera* gel. It has been shown that three years old *Aloe vera* contained significantly higher levels of polysaccharides. (Harry, 2013).

The most active among them is acemannan which is reported to have antiviral, antibacterial, wound healing and immune stimulative activity reduces radiation-induced skin reactions and stimulates hematopoiesis. It should be noticed that active glycoproteins have been also found in *Aloe vera* gel and may play some role in the therapeutic activity, either immunologically as lectins or as proteases (antibrady kinins). Moreover, *Aloe vera* gel has pH 4.4-4.7, consists primarily of water (98.5%) and polysaccharides and contains vitamins, enzymes, steroids etc. The gel when exposed to air rapidly oxidizes, decomposes and loses much of its biological activities, so there are different processing techniques with regard to gel's sterilization and stabilization. Because many of the active ingredients of *Aloe vera* gel appear to deteriorate on storage, the use of fresh gel is recommended (Harry, 2013).

There have been also, a few reports of harmful effects of *Aloe vera* gel such as eczema, allergic dermatitis or an increase in circulating leucocyte count probably as a result of stimulation of the immune system (Harry, 2013).

2.3 Mechanism of Actions - Uses and Applications of *Aloe vera*

2.3.1 Cosmetic Uses

Generally, *Aloe vera* has many uses both for humans and animals. Three distinct preparations of the plant are used: *Aloe vera* latex, *Aloe vera* gel and *Aloe vera* whole leaf extract, whose biological ingredients may act alone or in synergy. The use of *Aloe vera* in cosmetics is not new; there are many of them on the market which use *Aloe vera* in concentrations varying from 1 to 98%. It is well known that Aloe gel enables the plant to hold moisture for extremely long periods of time and has soothing effects as well 2. So, *Aloe vera* has found an extensive application in the cosmetic and toiletry industries, such as moisturizers, cleansers, sun lotions, toothpastes, mouthwashes, shaving creams, deodorants and shampoos. In Aloe-derived ingredients used in cosmetics, anthraquinone levels should not exceed 50 ppm, concentrations too low to induce phototoxicity. In the United States, the Food and Drug Administration (FDA) has approved the external use of *Aloe vera* gel only as a cosmetic ingredient (Raphael, 2012).

2.3.2 Food Uses

The food and beverage market is a promising arena for *Aloe vera*. It has been used as a resource of functional food such as yoghurt or for the preparation of health drinks, including tea. It is well known that botanical products are widely used as a nutritional supplement for the promotion of health or prevention of diseases. According to Serrano *et al.*, (2013), *Aloe vera* gel can be used as an edible coating to prolong the quality and safety of fresh products. Table grapes coated with Aloe gel significantly delayed the loss of functional compounds such as total phenolic and ascorbic acid. Indeed, *Aloe vera* inhibits the growth of microorganisms responsible for foodborne illness in humans or animals as well as food spoilage. *Aloe vera* does not appear to affect food taste or appearance, so it seems to be promising as a safe, natural and environmentally friendly alternative solution to conventional synthetic preservatives. FDA, in

the United States, has approved the internal use of gel as a “dietary supplement”. In the European Commission (EC) according to Annex I of Regulation No 1831/2003 *Aloe vera* can be used by the feed industries as a sensory additive functional group “flavouring compounds”, to increase the smell or palatability of feedings stuff (Alex, 2011).

2.4 Medicinal Uses

2.4.1 Healing Wounds

Due to polysaccharides and the growth hormone gibberellins, increased collagen and elastin formation may reduce wrinkling. The high healing capacity of *Aloe vera* is to find out a number of mucopolysaccharides (MPS) present between 10,000-20,000 MPS per litre 8. Moreover, *Aloe vera* effects are in the treatment of scar tissue and the prevention of scar formation following injury to the skin, probably are attributed to the activity of the amino acids necessary to new cell formation and due to the ability of its enzymes to promote regeneration of the deepest layers of the skin (Daniel, 2011)

2.4.2 Anti-inflammatory Action and Immunity Activity

The generation of prostaglandins from arachidonic acid is blocked by salicylic acid, which is both analgesic and anti-inflammatory. As a result, Aloe has been used to treat arthritis and joint disorders. Polysaccharides from *Aloe vera* boost immunity (Adekulle, 2012).

2.4.3 Effects on skin exposure to UV and X-radiation

Aloe vera supports the healing of first to second-degree burns although the exact role is not well known. It is suggested that lectin may be responsible for the therapeutic effect (Adekulle, 2012)

2.4.5 Effects on ulcers

Aloe vera can be used successfully in the general treatment of skin ulcers including mouth ulcers herpes simplex and psoriasis. Also, this plant was found to protect against the formation of gastric ulcers (Adekulle, 2012)

2.4.6 Antidiabetic Activities

Some inorganic elements (vanadium, manganese, copper) and especially the polysaccharides present in *Aloe vera* may have a significant role in antidiabetic activities. This plant has been linked with reduced blood glucose levels in diabetics and with lower blood lipid levels or cholesterol (approximately 30% lower) 40 in hyperlipidaemic patients (Adekulle, 2012)

2.4.7 Antioxidant Activities

Antioxidant activities have been studied. According to Lee *et al.*, (2012), *Aloe vera* activity was similar to that of α -tocopherol. Also, it has been noticed that the growth stage of the plant is important for such activities (Adekulle, 2012).

2.4.8 Laxative Effects and Antibacterial Properties

Anthraquinones present in *Aloe vera* latex is a potent laxative, increasing intestinal peristalsis (Adekulle, 2012). Many studies have found that *Aloe vera* suppresses the development of bacteria such as *Streptococcus pyogenes*, *Shigella flexneri*, and *Klebsiella* sp., particularly Gram-positive bacteria that cause food poisoning or infections in people and animals (Adekulle, 2012)

2.4.9 Antifungal Activity

Antifungal activity has received less attention, although inhibitory activity against *Candida* has been reported. For its antifungal properties, *Aloe vera* is used as a fish tank water conditioner (Adekulle, 2012).

2.4.10 Antiviral, Antitumor and Age-related Activity

These actions may be due to the indirect or direct effects: indirect through the stimulation of the immune system and direct to anthraquinones. So, clinical trials are in progress to obtain conclusive evidence for the use of *Aloe vera* in the treatment of HIV-AIDS or cancer. *Aloe vera* was investigated on pathogen-free rats with some promising results on age-related diseases (Adekulle, 2012).

2.5 The Use of *Aloe vera* in Animal Nutrition

Aloe vera apart from the above-mentioned uses seems to play an important role in promoting growth in chickens or their health management. Concerning broiler chickens, supplementing their basic feed with 600 mg kg⁻¹ Aloe powder, Aloe water extract, Aloe ethanol extract, or an extract combination of all three might boost production and immunological function, while the Aloe water extracts had better results than the others. Analogous were the findings of other researchers on the body weight of broilers when their drinking water was mixed with *Aloe vera* extract (5-30 cm³ per dm³ of water). On the other hand, broiler chickens fed with 0.1 or 0.2% *Aloe vera* had no significant effect on body weight. No significant results were found in the feed conversion ratio. Likewise, the dietary supplementation of *Aloe vera* did not significantly affect the carcass and sensory characteristics of the broiler meat. This finding is favorably compared with earlier reports on carcass yield and internal organs. On the contrary, other researchers observed that *Aloe vera* improved the acceptability of broiler meat (Michael, 2015).

Moreover, dietary *Aloe vera* had no effect on abdominal fat levels on breast and thigh muscle cholesterol levels or serum biochemistry (serum glucose, total cholesterol, HDL cholesterol, LDL cholesterol and triglycerides). Meanwhile, *Aloe vera* fed broilers showed significantly higher haemagglutination inhibition titer values against Newcastle disease. Also, it is reported that this plant can be used to treat and control coccidiosis in chickens (Michael, 2012)

The incorporation of *Aloe vera* in the laying hen diet resulted in a significant improvement in egg production (eggs/hen) but no difference was observed in feed consumption or feed conversion ratio. Furthermore, the dietary supplementation of *Aloe vera* extracts in laying hens may prevent or treat the effects of experimentally intoxicated lead on birds. Moreover, it is reported that a natural photogenic growth promoter, including *Aloe vera*, was used on the shrimp growth with promising results (Michael, 2012)

2.6 Properties of *Aloe vera*

Aloe vera has properties which have many medicinal uses. It has been observed through research that taking *Aloe vera* in food or drink has reduced the glucose level in the blood which has been useful in controlling diabetes. Most of the people who suffered from diabetes consumed *Aloe Vera* mixed with yoghurt or in the form of herbal tea. It has also been used in anti-ageing and anti-Wrinkle creams and moisturizers. The moisturizer or the cream is preferred as it is not oily or Sticky but dries up quickly as it is easily absorbed by the skin and does not have any type of odour. It can be applied to get relief from sunburn or other kinds of burn as it reduces the pain and the inflammation and gives relief from the burning sensation and heals the wound very quickly. The sap from inside the leaf can be used directly or the product that is made of pure *Aloe vera* extract can be used for application on the burn or the wound. The extract from *Aloe vera* can also be used for treating ulcers in the stomach. The

extract can be taken in juice form or with any food and it will help to reduce the inflammation and heal the wound in the stomach that is caused by the ulcer (Adekulle, 2012).

Irritable bowel syndrome, reflux, Crohn's disease, indigestion, heartburn, and a variety of other stomach illnesses can be relieved by drinking Aloe vera juice alone or mixed with other liquids. It helps to keep the acids in the stomach in balance, which has a relaxing effect on the stomach. Aloe vera has antibacterial and anti-inflammatory properties, which assist to treat oral and gum issues, as well as severe gum disease. It comes in the shape of a gel or toothpaste for massaging the gums. It may also be used to treat skin diseases including eczema, burns, and wounds from cuts (Adekulle, 2012).

2.6 Health Benefits of *Aloe Vera*

Aloe vera has been used from time immemorial to aid in smooth functioning of the gastrointestinal tract, mainly because of its properties of soothing, cleansing and helping the body to maintain healthy tissues. *Aloe vera* gel is famous for facilitating digestion, aiding blood and lymphatic circulation, as well as improving kidney, liver and gall bladder functions. *Aloe vera* has a minimum of three anti-inflammatory fatty acids, which help in the smooth functioning of the stomach, small intestines and colon. It has a natural property to alkalize digestive juices and prevents over-acidity, which is one of the common causes of digestive ailments. *Aloe vera* juice concentrates are high in essential enzymes, which stimulate digestion and liver functions. The synergistic effect of *Aloe vera* juice used in combination with a few other herbs does wonders as a liver-cleansing agent. *Aloe vera* supplements also contain a rare natural ingredient called Saponins, which is provided by nature to cleanse and flush out waste products and toxins. More medicinal uses of *Aloe vera* are described in the following sections. *Aloe vera* could be used to reduce the burning sensation of burns and blisters. Applying the

pure gel of *Aloe vera* would quell the sting of herpes. Juice or gel of *Aloe vera* is used to reduce warts, psoriasis and eczema. Today, skin doctors prescribe skin gels and creams made from *Aloe vera*. The fresh juice of *Aloe vera* is used to cure and heal rashes, vaginal infections, foot sores and fungus attacks of various types. It is one of the home remedies for these problems. *Aloe vera* is used in hair loss treatment (Adekulle, 2012).

The enzyme content of *Aloe vera* prevents hair loss by protecting the scalp against any diseases. *Aloe vera* also helps in the reduction of dandruff. You can mix the juice of *Aloe Vera* with coconut milk and wheat germ oil and massage your scalp before shampooing your hair. If used continuously it helps in hair re-growth. There are ongoing researches in the medical use of *Aloe vera* in the treatment and cure of AIDS and cancer. In the cure of cancer, there are many signs that medicines with *Aloe vera* content help in the activation of WBCs and in promoting the growth of non-cancerous cells. If people with HIV positive take regular doses of Aloe Vera, it helps in increasing the immunity of the body. The juice of *Aloe vera* mixed with milk is consumed for kidney infections. In Japan, *Aloe vera* is a main ingredient in yogurt. In India, *Aloe vera* is used to make certain food dishes. *Aloe vera* was used as medicine by the people of the ancient world. The Greeks believe Alexander the Great conquered the island of Socotra, an island in the Indian Ocean, because this island had ample growth of *Aloe vera* plants. *Aloe vera* is widely used for the following: Boosting of the immune system, as an anti-inflammatory for treating cuts and burns, providing nutritional supplements (Alexander, 2015).

2.7. External Benefits

2.7.1 Burn and Wound Healing

Aloe vera is best known for its soothing and healing effects on burns and other wounds. Studies show that *Aloe vera* when applied to a wound increases both the rate of wound closure and the

tensile strength of the wound via the proliferation of cells, including skin, liver, nerve and blood cells (Adekulle, 2012)

Ageing of The Skin: Aging of the skin is characterized by thinning and wrinkling of the epidermis, combined with the appearance of lines, creases, age spots and furrows in the face. Components of *Aloe vera* have been found to reverse degenerative skin changes by stimulating collagen and elastin synthesis, in essence turning back the clock on the effects ageing has on the skin (Adekulle, 2012).

2.7.2 Immune System Restoration

Research has proven that *Aloe vera* prevents suppression of the skin's immune system. This suppression may be one of the causes of skin cancer. In addition, topical application of the *Aloe vera* can be made up to 24 hours after exposure to ultraviolet light without reducing the degree of prevention regarding immune system suppression (Adekulle, 2012).

2.7.3 Moisturizer

One of the main reasons *Aloe vera* has become so popular among consumers is that it possesses incredible moisturizing properties. Studies show that *Aloe vera* improves the skin's ability to hydrate itself, aids in the removal of dead skin cells and has an effective penetrating ability that helps transport healthy substances through the skin. Each of these factors makes *Aloe vera* an ideal ingredient in cosmetic and dermatological products. In fact, *Aloe vera* is currently one of the most important ingredients in the cosmetics industry, being utilized in over 95% of the dermatologically valuable extracts are manufactured worldwide (Adekulle, 2012).

2.7.4 Arthritis, Joint and Muscle Pain

Aloe vera is believed to reduce severe joint and muscle pain associated with arthritis, as well as pain related to tendinitis and injuries. When applied directly to the area of pain, *Aloe vera* penetrates the skin to soothe the pain. Studies have also found that ingestion of *Aloe vera* on a daily basis can help prevent and cause a regression of adjuvant arthritis (Adekulle, 2012).

2.7.5 Anti-Inflammatory and Biological Vehicle

Aloe vera promotes a variety of anti-inflammatory responses in the body, reducing swelling from injuries and promoting recovery from infections. Such anti-inflammatory Responses not only aid in the relief of pain and discomfort, but also enhance the overall wound process (Adekulle, 2012). *Aloe vera* also acts as a biological carrier to let other bioactive compounds penetrate and absorb into deep tissue (Adekulle, 2012).

2.8 Internal Benefits

2.8.1 Arthritis, Joint and Muscle Pain

Aloe vera is believed to reduce severe joint and muscle pain associated with arthritis, as well as pain related to tendinitis and injuries. When applied directly to the area of pain, *Aloe vera* penetrates the skin to soothe the pain. Studies have also found that ingestion of *Aloe vera* on a daily basis can help prevent and cause a regression of adjuvant arthritis (Brandon, 2011).

2.8.2 Relieve Gastrointestinal Problems

Aloe vera juice can relieve gastrointestinal problems and may be one of the plant's most ancient uses. Even today, people drink the juice to help relieve ulcerous, gastrointestinal and kidney problems. People have described improved regularity, greater intestinal comfort and enhanced energy levels after ingesting *Aloe vera* juice. In addition, many who have suffered from

indigestion, irritable bowel syndrome, increased stomach acid, peptic and duodenal ulcers, and colitis have reported relief from these conditions following ingestion of *Aloe vera* juice (Brandon, 2011)

2.8.3 Coronary Heart Disease

Coronary heart disease is one of the major causes of death in the United States. However, studies suggest that the ingestion of *Aloe vera* gel may have a beneficial effect on the accumulation of blood fat lipids associated with the disease. Test groups given *Aloe vera* showed a decrease in total cholesterol, triglyceride, phospholipid and non esterified fatty acid levels, each of which, when elevated, seem to accelerate the accumulation of fatty material in large and medium-sized arteries, including the coronary arteries of the heart (Brandon, 2011)

2.8.4 Antioxidant and Blood Circulation

Antioxidant, anti-microbial and anti-viral--*Aloe vera* contains vitamin C, E, zinc and seven superoxide dismutase (Brandon, 2011). Also, a number of *Aloe vera* constituents have beneficial effects on blood pressure and coagulation (Brandon, 2011)

2.8.5 Digestion

One of its most popular usages these days is in helping any type of digestive or bowel disorder. *Aloe vera* has received an enormous amount of positive Press for its benefits in helping IBS, irritable bowel syndrome. It is also useful with other digestive problems, including peptic ulcers or any type of stomach inflammation. Its properties are those of healing and soothing and so it is worth using as a part of a healing programme on any digestive complaint (Brandon, 2011)

2.8.6 Immune system, Burns and Sunburn

Aloe vera contains many ingredients providing antibacterial, antiviral and analgesic elements (Brandon, 2011). The soothing and healing quality of *Aloe vera* are well known for any type of burn and is especially popular for sunburn (Brandon, 2011).

2.8.7 Laxative and Detoxification

It has a gentle laxative effect on the bowels. Amino acids assist the liver and kidneys. The precise method by which *Aloe vera* works is not yet fully understood, but it is a great stimulator of the body's own immune system, which counteracts disease and disorder (Brandon, 2011)

2.9 Medicinal Uses of *Aloe Vera*

Aloe vera plays an important role in maintaining the healthy functioning of the major organs and Preventing diseases.

- *Aloe vera* releases pepsin, which aids digestion, soothes digestive tract irritations, colic pain and ulcers. It also heals heartburns. This has come down from the traditions of folk medicine of Europe and proved in recent clinical trials in Japan. *Aloe vera* acts as a general tonic, raises immunity and fights diseases. Research reveals its efficacy in conditions like HIV and cancer, especially leukaemia, due to its ability to produce white blood cells. Consequently, it can minimize the side effects of chemotherapy and radiation.
- It boosts circulation, and thus increases the supply of oxygen to the cells. Therefore, it could play a major role in alleviating the condition of thalassemia patients.
- *Aloe vera* is also beneficial for Asthma patients.
- It helps to maintain healthy joints and muscles, and thus, prevents arthritis.

- *Aloe vera* detoxifies the body and is considered the best colon cleanser. It prevents constipation; therefore, it is an effective blood purifier.
- It is beneficial in kidney and liver problems, like jaundice.
- *Aloe vera* also reduces blood sugar and controls diabetes.
- It reduces cholesterol and triglycerides, leading to a healthy heart, and preventing cardiac problems.
- *Aloe vera* reduces inflammation and infection of the eye and ear.
- Finally, it provides energy and acts as a restorative. Moreover, it is said to alleviate depression (Brandon, 2011)

2.10 *Aloe vera* for a Healthy Skin

Apart from its effect on the internal organs, *Aloe vera* has a beneficial effect on the skin.

- It is rich in antioxidants, which neutralize free radicals. As a result, *Aloe vera* wards off wrinkles and age-related changes.
- It nourishes the skin, by boosting the circulatory system.
- *Aloe vera* is effective in treating skin disorders, like dermatitis, and even psoriasis.
- It heals cuts and wounds, blisters and burns, including sunburns, and even minor second-degree burns.
- *Aloe vera* clears acne and skin allergies, dark spots and skin blemishes, and makes the skin clearer.
- It is also good for the hair and scalp (Mathew, 2011)

In the scientific community, there has been a divergent theory on the application and workability Of *Aloe Vera*. But in the last 20 years with the advent of intensified scientific research, evidence has been fully established, demonstrating its diverse medicinal properties.

Some of these evidential *Aloe vera* medicinal uses and *Aloe vera* Juice health benefits are for the treatment of the following health conditions:

Canker Sores (Aphthous stomatitis) *Aloe Vera* Gel may treat recurrent aphthous ulcers, reduce pain and increase the amount of time between the appearances of new ulcers

Dry Skin: Traditionally Aloe has been used as a moisturizer. Studies suggest that Aloe may effectively reduce skin dryness.

Lichen Planus: Studies suggest that Lichen Planus, which is a chronic inflammatory disease that affects the lining of the mouth, maybe treated by Aloe.

Skin Burns/Skin Ulcers: It has been found that *Aloe vera* may aid in healing of mild to moderate skin burns and ulcers. Extensive research carried out since the 1930s has shown that the clear Aloe Gel has a dramatic ability to heal wounds, ulcers and burns by putting a protective coating on the affected areas and speeding up the healing rate.

Radiation Dermatitis: Reports in the 1930s of tropical Aloe's beneficial effects on skin after radiation exposure, lead to widespread use in skin products. Currently, *Aloe vera* Gel is sometimes recommended for skin irritation caused by prolonged exposure to radiation.

Constipation: Dried latex from the inner lining of Aloe leaves has been used traditionally as a laxative taken by mouth. Although few studies have been conducted to assess this effect on Aloe in humans, the laxative properties of Aloe components such as aloin are well supported by scientific evidence.

Genital Herpes: Evidence from human studies suggests that extracts from *Aloe vera* in a hydrophilic cream may be an effective treatment of genital herpes in men.

Psoriasis Vulgaris: Early evidence suggests that an extract from Aloe in hydrophilic cream may be an effective treatment of Psoriasis Vulgaris.

Seborrheic Dermatitis (Seborrhea, Dandruff): A study of *Aloe vera* lotions suggests effectiveness for treating seborrheic dermatitis when applied to the skin.

Cancer Prevention: There is early evidence that oral Aloe may reduce the risk of developing lung cancer. *Aloe vera* is used in alternative medicines and home first aid (Mathew, 2011)

2.11 Side Effects of *Aloe vera*

Some people do experience side effects when using *Aloe vera*. Some of these are:

1. Dehydration due to frequent stools
2. Stomach cramping
3. Irregular heartbeat
4. Lowered potassium levels

In addition, you should not take *Aloe vera* internally if you have:

1. Kidney problems
 2. Heart disease
 3. Diabetes
 4. Pregnant
 5. Nursing
- Allergies to onions, garlic, or tulips (Mathew, 2011)

2.12 Effect on HIV

Aloe Vera contains Glucomannan, a special complex polysaccharide composed largely of the sugar Mannose. It interacts with special cell-surface receptors on those cells which repair damaged tissues, called fibroblasts, stimulating them, activating their faster growth and replication. An extract of Mannose, one of the sugars in *Aloe vera* can inhibit HIV-1, the virus associated with AIDS. In a 1991 study in Molecular Biotherapy, HIV-1 cells were treated in vitro outside the body with the Mannose extract. Virus reproduction was reduced by as much as 30% by Aloe Vera, viral load total amount of the virus as well as reduced, the spread of the

virus from the infected cells was suppressed and the viability chance of survival of infected (Alexander, 2012).

CHAPTER THREE

3.0 MATERIALS AND METHODS

3.1 Study Design

The study was an experimental, laboratory-based study, which was carried out at the laboratory of the Biology Department, Al-Qalam University Katsina, Katsina State, Nigeria.

3.2 Plant Material Used

Fresh leaves of *A. Vera* were collected from the biological garden of Al-Qalam University Katsina, Katsina, in February 2022. The fresh leaves were washed with distilled water and air-dried. After drying, leaves were powdered and stored at 4°C in airtight bottles for further study.

3.3 Extraction

0.3 grams of Aloe vera leaves grounded and added with 50 ml of chloroform, n-hexane, ethyl acetate and double distilled water in separate flasks for phytonutrients extraction for 48 hours. These solutions were filtered by using Whatman filter paper of forty-two size and the solutions were extracted. The extracts were further used for the determination of various phytonutrients.

3.4 Qualitative Tests for Phytochemicals

Qualitative tests for Phytochemical were carried out on the different extracts and the powdered samples. The standard methods for the identification of the components of the samples described by, Ogbuewu (2008), Trease (2003), and Sofowar (2003) were used.

3.4.1 Phlobatannins Test

The presence of phlobatannins was confirmed by the formation of red precipitate by boiling the chloroform extract of each sample with 1% HCl.

3.4.2 Flavonoid Test

Ammonia solution (5ml) was added to a small portion of filtrate of chloroform extract followed by the addition of concentrated H₂SO₄. A yellow colouration observed in each extract indicated the presence of flavonoids. The yellow colouration disappears on standing.

3.4.3 Steroids Test

In this test 2ml of acetic anhydride and 2ml of H₂SO₄ were added to 5ml extract from each sample. Change of colour blue from violet would indicate the presence of steroids.

3.4.4 Cardiac Glycosides Test

Cardiac glycosides: Five millilitres of each sample juice was treated with two millilitres of glacial acetic acid containing one drop of FeCl₃ solution, this was under layered with 1 millilitre of conc. H₂SO₄. A brown ring shows the deoxy sugar characteristics of cardenolides. Sometimes a violet ring may form indicating cardiac glycoside.

3.4.5 Tannins Test

Five milliliters of extract were taken and boiled with 20ml of CHCl₃. In the addition of 0.1 %, FeCl₃ solution to the filtrate and appearance of brownish colour shows the presence of tannin.

3.4.6 Saponins test

About five milliliters of citrus sample was taken and boiled in 20 milliliters of CHCl₃ and filtered. To the 10 millilitre filtrate added five milliliters of double distilled water with 3 drops of olive oil, emulsion formation shows the presence of saponins.

3.4.7 Terpenoids Test

Five milliliter of the sample was added to 2 milliliter of CHCl_3 and three milliliter of conc. H_2SO_4 . The formation of reddish brown colour would show the presence of terpenoids.

3.5 Experimental Animals

Four rabbits (mean weight 1.7kg), were acclimatized for 7 days and divided into two groups of two each. The rabbits were dewormed and all physiological parameters monitored were within the normal range for healthy animals. Fresh Aloe vera leaves were obtained from the Botanical Garden, Al-Qalam University, Katsina and washed with clean water. The skin of each Aloe vera leaf was peeled off to reveal the gel which was homogenized to a fine texture with a blender, centrifuged and the supernatant separated from the residue. Little water was added to the supernatant to reduce its viscosity and the extract was refrigerated at 4°C .

3.6 Wound Creation and Treatment

The paravertebral region of the rabbit was moistened, washed with soap and water, shaved and cleaned with cotton wool moistened with methylated spirit to disinfect the area. The site was locally-blocked with 2% lignocaine double diluted to 5ml and administered 0.2ml subcutaneously. A pin-prick non-response indicated effective anaesthesia. A pair of wounds (2cm x 2cm each) was created on the superficial epidermis of the skin of each rabbit using a cardboard template, scalpel and thumb forceps. Each wound was lavaged with normal saline using a needle and syringe. The day of wound creation marked day 0 of the experiment.

The wounds were topically treated with the Aloe vera gel dispensed with a syringe. The wounds on control rabbits were treated with 0.9% normal saline. This wound treatment was done daily from day 0 until the wound scabs fell off representing the termination of the experiment. The

wounds were measured daily by placing the Vernier caliper on the wound edges dorsally and ventrally, and readings were recorded until scabs fell off.

3.7 Data Analysis

The data obtained were presented as Mean \pm Standard Error of Mean and analyzed using the one-way analysis of variance, and a P-value lower than 0.05 was considered significant. Data were double entered into an excel spread sheet (Excel version 5.0, Microsoft Excel) ANOVA was conducted using SPSS Version 28.0.1.1 (14) and results were expressed as a table.

CHAPTER FOUR

4.0 RESULTS

4.1 Qualitative Phytochemical Screening of *Aloe vera*

The qualitative phytochemical analysis was carried out on different samples of the *Aloe vera* to detect the presence or absence of bioactive components of *Aloe vera* using chloroform, distilled water, ethyl acetate and n-haxane as extracts as shown in the table 4.1 below.

Table 4.1 Identified Bioactive Components of *Aloe vera*

Extracts	Tannins	Saponins	Phlobo tannins	Flavonoid	Steroids	Terpenoids	Cardiac glycosides
Chloroform	+	+	-	+	+	+	+
Distilled water	+	+	-	+	-	+	-
Ethyl acetate	+	+	-	+	+	+	+
n-Hexane	+	+	-	-	+	+	+

Key: + = Present, - = Absent

4.2 Effects on Wound Contraction Observed at the Proliferative and Maturation Phases of Wound Healing

Give a brief explanation of the table

Table 4.2: *Aloe vera* Effect on Wound Contraction in Rabbits

Phase	Experimental	Control	t	95% confidence interval of the difference		P-Value
					Upper	
				Lower		
Inflammatory	39.75±6.71	59.22±11.66	1.56	-47.28	8.33	0.041
Proliferative	3.89±1.47	12.91±3.99	2.64	-16.64	-1.40	0.025
Maturation	2.05±0.63	9.64±2.97	3.46	-12.48	-2.70	0.006

Key: Mean values ± Standard deviation

CHAPTER FIVE

5.0 DISCUSSION, CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

5.1 DISCUSSION

The test performed on chloroform extract shows that tannins, saponins, terpenoids, flavonoids, cardiac glycosides and steroids were positive and for phlobotannins were negative.

The test performed on n-hexane also shows for tannins, saponins, cardiac glycosides, steroids and terpenoids were positive while for phlobotannins and flavonoids were negative. The Ethyl acetate extract used for testing of tannins, flavonoids, saponins, steroids, terpenoids, and cardiac glycosides showed positive while for phlobotannins were negative. The Double distilled water test showed for tannins, saponins, flavonoids and terpenoids were positive and for phlobotannins and steroids was negative.

Wound healing is a systematic process which is described using three overlapping phases namely inflammatory, proliferative and maturation. This study showed that Aloe vera gel improved the rate of wound healing in rabbits as depicted by shorter days of healing- when the scab fell off within 9 days compared to the control (mean 12 days). This could be due to the presence of pro-healing ingredients such as vitamin C, amino acids, vitamin E and zinc.¹⁸

Treatment of wounds in rabbits with Aloe vera gel produced significant ($P < 0.05$) effects on wound contraction especially during the proliferative and maturation phases of wound healing (Table 2). This could have been due the presence of phytochemicals in Aloe vera such as flavonoids and saponins which are useful in protecting and repairing damaged tissues of plants and animals. Also, glucomannan, a mannose-rich polysaccharide and gibberellin, a growth hormone present in the gel could have partly played important roles in faster wound healing by interacting with the growth factor receptors which in turn stimulated the activity and proliferation of fibroblasts and promoted collagen synthesis similar to earlier reports.

In conclusion, Aloe vera gel produced significant and positive effects on wound contraction in the experimental animals. It would be necessary to further investigate these findings with a view to discovering more uses of aloe vera plant in the animal species apart from its wound healing effects.

5.2 Conclusion

The sample of *Aloe vera* used in this study revealed the presence of medicinally active constituents like tannins, saponins, phlobbasstannis, steroid, terpenoids, flavonoids, and cardiac glycosides. *Aloe vera* gel also has a significant and positive effect on wound healing in the experimental rabbits and these findings will go a long way in expanding the horizon of clinical application of this plant in solving wound healing problems in both humans and other animal species.

5.3 Recommendation

- There is a need for scientific evaluation, standardization and safety evaluation of *Aole vera* as a herbal ointments.
- When using Aloe Vera for the purpose of wound healing, it is also recommended to infuse other methods of treatment whether *Aloe vera* is being used as the primary treatment or complementary treatment.

REFERENCES

- Adnan, M.J. *et al.*, (2015). Study of the efficacy of Aloe vera extracts in treatment of non-infected wounds induced by sulphuric acid and infected wounds with *Staphylococcus aureus*. *International Journal Advanced Research Chemical Science*, 3: 593-601.
- Ayyanar, D. and Ignacimuthu M. (2009). *Therapeutic and medicinal uses of Aloe vera: review*. *Science Research*, 4: 599-610.
- Babak, D., *et al.*, (2011). Effects of different levels of Aloe vera gel as an alternative to antibiotic on performance and ileum morphology in broilers. *Italian Journal of Animal Science*, 10: 189-194.
- Barreto, R.S. *et al.*, (2014). *A systematic review of the wound healing effects of mono-terpenes and iridoid derivatives*. *Public Medline*, 19: 846-862.
- Brandon S.S. (2011). Aloe vera an ancient herb for modern. Dentistry-a literature. *Journal of Dental Surgery*, 10: 1-6.
- Chan, E.W.C., *et al.*, (2008). *Antioxidant and tyrosinase inhibition properties of leaves and rhizomes of ginger species*. *Food Chemistry*, 109: 477-483.
- Daniel, S. (2011). Aloe vera their chemicals composition and applications: a review. *International Journal of Biology & Medicine Research*, 2: 466-471.
- Harry, R. (2013). Biological activities of Aloe vera. *International Journal of Pharm Technology*, 2: 259-580.
- James, S. (2012). Therapeutic effects of Aloe vera on cutaneous microcirculation and wound healing in second degree burn model in rats. *Journal of the Medical Association of Thailand*, 83: 417-25.
- Kumara, M., *et al.*, (2001). Efficacy of Buteamono sperma on dermal wound healing in rats. *International Journal of Biochemistry and Cell Biology*, 37: 566-573.

- Langendam, M. W. *et al.* (2010) 'Tips and tricks for understanding and using SR results - no 17: an introduction to the GRADE approach; rating the quality of evidence for an intervention', *Evidence-Based Child Health: A Cochrane Review Journal*, 5(2), pp. 537–540. doi: 10.1002/ebch.503.
- Martins, S. (2014). Effects of topical medications on the healing of open pad wounds in dogs. *Journal of the American Animal Hospital Association*, 28: 499-502.
- Mendonca, F.A., *et al.*, (2009). Effects of the application of Aloe vera (L.) and micro current on the healing of wounds surgically induced in wistar rats. *Acta Cirurgica Brasileira*, 24: 150-5.
- Micheal, B. (2012). Wound healing activity of topical application of Aloe vera gel in experimental animal models. *International Journal of Pharma and Bio Sciences*, 3: 63-72.
- Moghbel, A., *et al.*, (2007). Wound healing and toxicity evaluation of Aloe vera cream on outpatients with second degree patient. *International Journal of Pharmacy and Pharmaceutical Sciences*, 3: 157-160.
- Moriyama, B. *et al.*, (2002). Evaluation of antioxidant potential of Aloe vera (Aloe barbadensis Miller) extracts. *Journal of Agricultural and Food Chemistry*, 51: 7788-7791.
- Muller, M.J., *et al.*, (2003). Retardation of wound healing by silver sulphadiazine is reversed by Aloe vera and nystatin. *Burns*, 29: 834- 836.
- Nasrin, T, *et al.*, (2009). Influence of Aloe vera gel on dermal wound healing process in rat. *Toxicology Mechanisms and Methods*, 19: 73-77.
- Oryan, A., *et al.*, (2010). Effect of aqueous extract of Aloe vera on experimental cutaneous wound healing in rat. *Veterinarski Arhiv*, 80: 509-522.

- Park, S. E. and Thomas, J. (2018) 'Evidence synthesis software', *BMJ Evidence-Based Medicine*, 23(4), pp. 140–141. doi: 10.1136/bmjebm-2018-110962.
- Rajar, U.D.M., *et al.*, (2008). Efficacy of Aloe vera gel in the treatment of vulval lichen planus. *Journal College of Physiology and Surgery Pakistan*, 18: 612-614.
- Raphael G. (2012). *Influence of Aloe vera on collagen characteristics in healing dermal wounds in rats*. *Molecular and Cellular Biochemistry*, 181: 71-6.
- Reddy, C.H.U., *et al.*, (2010). Aloe vera- a wound healer. *Asian Journal of Oral Head Allied Sciences*, 1: 91-92.
- Rodríguez, D.J., *et al.*, (2005). *Antifungal activity in vitro of Aloe vera pulp and liquid fraction against plant pathogenic fungi*. *Industrial Crops and Products*, 21: 81-87.
- Rodriguez, M.B., *et al.*, (2008). *Comparative evaluation of Aloe vera in the management of burn wounds in guinea pigs*. *Plastic and Reconstructive Surgery*, 8: 386-389.
- Sumitra, M., *et al.*, (2005). Efficacy of Buteamono sperma on dermal wound healing in rats. *International Journal of Biochemistry and Cell Biology*, 37: 566-573.

APPENDIX